

PERFORMANCE-DETERMINANT NEXUS OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN NIGERIA

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Key words: Small and Medium enterprises, Credit to SMEs, Electricity Consumption by SMEs, Performance	Abstract: <i>The study investigated the determinants of performance of small and medium size enterprises in Nigeria from 1986-2024. The model formulated used SME Output as the dependent variable proxy for performance while data on exchange rate, interest rate, and credit to SMEs and electricity consumption, crime rate were used as independent variables used as the determinants of performance. By using the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) technique, findings showed that in the long-run, electricity consumption by SMEs had a positive but insignificant relationship with the performance of SMEs in Nigeria over the period studied. In the short-run, interest rate had a positive but insignificant relationship on SMES Output while in the long-run, the relationship was negative. The effect of exchange rate on SMEs Output was both positive in the short and long-run period even though it was only positively significant in the long-run. In the long-run, access to credit exerted positive but insignificant growth on SMEs Output while crime rate exerted a significantly negative effect on SMEs Output in both the short and long-run periods. In conclusion, electricity consumption, access to credit and reduction in crime are the short-term determinants of performance of SMEs while in the long-run, chief determinants are lower interest rate, stable exchange rate and reduced crime rate. The study therefore recommends that a single-digit interest is necessary to reduce the cost of borrowing funds which will stimulate more SME operators to access funds for their businesses. SMEs should engage in the mass production of quality products that will appeal to local and international market. This way, they will have access to foreign currencies and thus hedge against the effect of depreciation of the naira. Adequate security should be provided by the Nigeria Police Force and other sister agencies with adequate funding provided. The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission should live up to their responsibility of dealing with the issue of financial and internet fraud. This will boost local and foreign investors' confidence within the Nigerian economy.</i>
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1. INTRODUCTION

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) have been identified as the primary source of growth and development in most economies of the world. They account for the majority of businesses worldwide and are important contributors to job creation and global economic development (World Bank, 2022). In developing countries, they account for a considerable percentage of all businesses in the “formal sector” and have been recognized as the engine of growth in these economies as they play the crucial role of employment creation, poverty reduction, innovative thinking and entrepreneurship (Adeosun & Shittu, 2021). As reported by World Bank (2022), SMEs in emerging economies contribute up to 40% to Gross Domestic Product (GDP), more than 50% of employment worldwide and constitute about 90% of businesses across countries of the world. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), SMEs employ more than 84% of Nigerian workers and comprise roughly 96% of all enterprises (NBS, 2020). In Nigeria, The SMEDAN/NBS MSME Survey (2017) indicate that Nigeria’s SMEs account for 49.78% of the country’s GDP and provides over 80% of employment in the country (PwC, 2020). Eniola (2014) opined that regardless of the exploitation of crude oil, SMEs still accounts for 70% of

employment of the country’s total population. It is a major driver of industrialization, modernization, rural-urban development, gainful employment, hence contributing to increase per capital income and promoting equitable distribution of income thereby improving the welfare and quality of life of the citizens (Aremu&Adeyemi cited in Eniola, 2014). According to Ikpore, Nnabu and Itumo (2017), the prevailing economic condition of 1970s and early 1980s in Nigeria was responsible for the adoption of industrialization strategies based on large scale production. This derives from the fact that numerous large scale industries were set up during the rehabilitation program of the post-war era of 1970s. These industries were capital intensive and required the importation of heavy machines and technical manpower to man these capitals. These unchecked importations asserted negative impact on foreign exchange earnings in Nigeria. Due to the inherent problems associated to the poor performances of the large scale enterprises in Nigeria, it became imperative for government to device means to promote and propagate small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) as a panacea to achieve self-reliant and sustainable economic growth within the country. Given this recognition of the SMEs as a reliable pathway for sustained growth and development, successive governments in Nigeria

Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

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have given maximum support to SMEs through various interventions such as the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) intervention funds and the National Enterprises Development Programme (NEDEP), Which was mandated to provide training, access to finance, and market linkages to SMEs. Also set up were Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) and Nigerian Agricultural Cooperative Bank to enhance lending to agriculture and SMEs.

Despite these interventions, SMEs in Nigeria have not performed well when compared with its counterparts from Ghana and South Africa, (Aremu, M. A., & Olodo, H.O. (2015). For instance, according to the association of Ghana Industries report, SMEs in Ghana contribute approximately 70% to Ghana's GDP and account for about 92% of businesses in the country (International Trade Center, 2016). Similarly, according to the Small Business Institute and the Small Business Project, SMEs contributed approximately 52% of total economic output in South Africa in 2019 (Small Business Institute, 2021). In Nigeria, their contribution to GDP is 48% despite making up 96% of all businesses. Nigeria also records a significant number of business registrations but also note a concerning number of deregistration due to business failures (Corporate Affairs Commission, 2022). The issue of SME failure is not transient; rather, it persists over various economic cycles and policy changes. This continuity of failure highlights the

structural and systemic challenges that hinder SME sustainability (Abdul, 2022).

Given the unstable macroeconomic environment coupled with worsening crime in Nigeria, it becomes imperative to evaluate crime rate and some macroeconomic variables to determine how they affect the performance of these businesses in Nigeria. Electricity consumption per capita, interest and exchange rates are used to proxy macroeconomic variables while crime rate proxies the frequency of occurrence of crime in the country within the period of the study. SME output as a share of GDP is used to proxy performance. The researcher wishes to evaluate these variables in order ascertain how they relate to the performance of SMEs in Nigeria. Hence, the study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There is no central definition of 'Small and Medium Enterprises'. Its definition varies across countries and even organisations. According to Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (2006), SMEs are those enterprises that have a total minimum capital of one million, five hundred thousand naira and maximum of two hundred million naira, including working capital but, cost of land and a minimum staff strength of ten and a maximum of three hundred. SMEDAN (2005) defines SMEs in terms of size. It considers small scale enterprises are businesses with ten to forty-nine people with an annual turnover of five to forty-nine million Naira

Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

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while a medium scale enterprises is one that has fifty to one hundred and ninety-nine employees with a year turnover of fifty to four hundred and ninety-nine million Naira. In Nigeria, SMEs cover economic activities within all sectors.

The study was anchored on the resources-based view (RBV) theory, first proposed by Wernerfelt (1984). He argued that organizations' unique and unmatched capabilities and resources are the reason to create competitive advantage. Later, many researchers argued that organizations' unmatched and rare capabilities that are inimitable create competencies (Astuti and Datrini, 2021). Based on the assumption of RBV theory, an organization's resources and unique competencies are the main sources that improve business performances (Muangmee et al., 2019). Organization competencies have a wide range that covers many aspects depending upon the circumstances in which it operates (Hitt et al., 2011). There are external and internal threats that affect business performances and a firm with an innovative strategy would better compete to the environmental circumstances (Asadi et al., 2021).

Empirically, the effect of power distribution on the efficiency of SMEs in southern Taraba State was studied by Giwa, Rikwetishe, and Abomchi (2023). The research's stated goals were to determine the impact of power supply stability on the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the study region and

further determine the cost-effectiveness of power supply on SMEs' performance. Primary data was collected by open-ended questionnaires and used in the research. Fourteen hundred and eleven managers from small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the Southern Zone (IBI, Wukari, Donga, Takum, and Ussa) were interviewed using a simple random selection method. Out of the total number of questionnaires distributed, only 105 (or 92.12%) were complete and usable for the research. Ordinary least squares and descriptive statistics were used in it. Power supply reliability and cost had a favorable and statistically significant influence on the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the research area. Researchers in Southern Taraba state concluded that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) benefit from increased power distribution. Consequently, it was suggested that to boost the profitability of SMEs in Nigeria, the government should provide a consistent and reliable supply of power and lower energy rates for SMEs. Okeke, Anetoh, Obiezekwem, Anetoh, Okafor, Ebomah and Ikpo (2020) carried out a research on Effect of Economic Indicators on the Performance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Nigeria. The study examined the effects of inflation rate, interest rate and exchange rate on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises with a particular reference to south-eastern geographical area.

Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

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The study adopted a cross sectional survey research design. The population of the study was 1560 while the sample size was 296. Multiple regression analysis statistical technique was used to test the hypotheses formulated to guide the study. It was found that inflation, interest rate and exchange rate have significant negative effect on the performance of SMES in South-East, Nigeria. The study recommended an efficient management of inflation rate in such a way to stimulate the economic growth. Government and policy makers should regulate interest rates and other credit facilities, in order to ensure funds accessibility for all SMES in Nigeria and at affordable rates. Employing secondary data spanning 1998 to 2017.

Olaoye, Adedeji and Yyeni-Agbaje (2018) explored the impact of commercial bank lending to small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) on Nigerian economy. The study applied correlation analysis, ordinary least square regression and Granger causality test. The findings revealed that commercial bank loans to SMEs has a negative but not significant impact on gross domestic product (GDP); Average commercial bank lending rate to SMEs has a negative but not significant impact on GDP; and inflation rate has a positive but not significant effect on GDP. The study also found that there is no causal relationship between the independent variables (commercial bank loans to SMEs, average commercial bank lending rate to SMEs

and inflation rate) and the dependent variable (GDP – A proxy for Nigerian economy).

Asogwa, O., & Ibrahim, R., & Oyedepo, J. (2023) established that armed robbery attacks led to early business closures in high-risk areas. Kidnapping is a growing concern for Nigerian SMEs, particularly in the northern regions. Adebayo and Lawal (2022) found that investor confidence declined by 45% in areas prone to kidnapping, leading to a reduction in SME investments. Bashir and Ibrahim (2021) reported that SMEs in rural areas suffered disproportionately due to slow government responses to kidnapping cases. Theft negatively impacts SME profitability and operational efficiency.

Adeleke (2020) found that SMEs in Lagos State faced a significant decline in sales due to armed robbery, prompting businesses to implement additional security measures. Bamiduro and Rauf (2020) analyzed the effects of theft on SMEs in Nigeria, using a sample of 590 SMEs, and found that theft led to increased financial losses and heightened security costs. Yahaya, I., Adebayo, O., & Adedeji, A. (2022) established that SMEs in conflict-prone areas suffer from supply chain disruptions and reduced revenue. Likewise, Omole and Agbo (2020) found that communal conflicts in Nigeria led to business closures, exacerbating unemployment.

3. METHODOLOGY.

Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

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The study adopted an ex-post facto time series research design to examine the relationship between SME Output as a share of GDP, electricity consumption per capita, interest rate, exchange rate, access to credit, crime rate as dependent and independent variables respectively. The study heavily relied on secondary data. The annual data on small and medium size performance (proxy by SME output as a percentage of gross domestic product), exchange rate and interest rate were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin 2024 edition while electricity consumption per capita and crime rate were sourced from World Bank Development Indicator (World Bank Database) 2024 edition. The study adapted and modified the model of Ogunleye and Obiora (2007) who worked on structural economy reform and the performance of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria SMEs. Their model was a modified production function that was complimented by a series of selected variables usually introduced in the growth models.

Their model was specified thus;

$SGDP$

$$= f(GSSME, PI, INTR, NEX, LED) \dots \dots \dots 3.1$$

Where,

$SGDP$ = SME Share of GDP

$GSSME$ = Government Expenditure on SMEs

PI = Political Instability

NE = Net Export

LED = Level of Educational Development

The above model was then modified to accommodate the variables of this study thus;

$SMEO$

$$= f(ELEC, INTR, EXCR, SMEC, CR) \dots \dots \dots$$

Equation 3.2 was further econometrically transformed into the form below for easy estimation

$$\ln SMEO_t = a_0 + a_1 \ln ELEC_t + a_2 \ln EXCR_t + a_3 \ln INTR_t + a_4 \ln SMEC_t + a_5 \ln CR_t + U_t \dots \dots \dots -3.3$$

Where

$SMEO$ = SME Output (proxy for performance of SMEs in Nigeria)

$ELEC$ = Electricity Consumption

$INTR$ = Interest Rate

$EXCR$ = Exchange Rate

$SMEC$ = SME Credit

CR = Crime Rate

$a_0 - a_5$ = Coefficients of independent variables

U = Error term.

t = Time period

4. ANALYSIS

Using trend analysis as a descriptive tool as seen below, **Fig. 4.1**, showed that SMEs output was 9.36% of GDP in 1986. This increased to 15.24% in 1990 but dropped slightly to 13.43% in 1992. Fluctuations in SMEs output resulted in 20.37% SMEs contribution to Nigeria's GDP by 2016. The year 2016 marked significant milestone for SMEs performance in Nigeria as the 20.37% recorded that year was the highest for the period

Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

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under study. This may have been as a result of increased government intervention in SMEs in the form of grants and loans. However, SMEs share of GDP dropped slightly to 11.67% in 2024. In Figure 4.2, electricity consumption fluctuated around 80 to 130kw/c since 1986. Specifically, consumption of electricity reached a period high of 158.9kw/c in 2016 and a period low of 69kw/c in 1996. For SMEs that depend on electricity, the consumption is low when compared with other developing countries in Africa.

Furthermore, interest rate averaged 23% from 1986 through 2000. Figure 4.3 showed the trend of interest rate for the period 1986 – 2024. The Figure showed that interest rate revolved around 25% since 2009 reaching 27.72% in 2024. With interest rate at double digit of 27.72%, SMEs may be dissuaded from borrowing especially when inflation rate is significantly higher in 2024 compared to previous years.

Since exchange rate is a potential determinant of SMEs performance, the trend of exchange rate as seen in Fig. 4.5 above shows steady increase in

exchange rate from ₦2.02 in 1986 to ₦8.04 in 1990 and ₦153 in 2010. Exchange rate increased further to ₦401.15 in 2020 before reaching ₦1,480 in 2024.

Figure 4.5 above shows that SMEs credit peaked at ₦371bn in 2024 up from the previous year's figure of ₦355bn. This implies that there is increased access to credit to SMEs and this is expected to exert positive effect on their performance.

Figure 4.6 below shows the trend of crime rate in Nigeria for the period under study. The trend shows that crime rate decreased significantly from 43.3% in 1986 to 10.15% in 1998. Evidence from Figure 4.6 above further reveals that crime rate rose significantly in 2009 reaching 44.03% as against 34% recorded in 2008. The 44.03% recorded in 2009 marked the highest crime rate in Nigeria since 1986 and it portends serious consequences for SMEs as they seek to increase their output. As at end of 2024, crime rate in Nigeria was 21.8%.

Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

Figure 4.1: SMEs output as % of GDP (Source: CBN, 2024)

Fig. 4.2: trend of electricity consumption per capita

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Fig. 4.3: Trend of interest rate (Source: CBN, 2024)

Figure 4.4: Trend of exchange rate in Nigeria (Source: CBN, 2024)

Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

Fig. 4.5: Trend of access to credit to SMEs (Source: CBN, 2024)

Fig. 4.6: Trend of crime rate in Nigeria (Source: CBN, 2024)

Unit Root Test

The ADF Unit root test was conducted to ascertain whether the variables in the model are

stationary and at what level. The summary of unit root tests (ADF) results using E-views software is detailed in the table below:

Table 4.1: Summary of ADF test results at 5% critical value

Variables	ADF Test Statistics		Order of Integration	Decision Rule
	@ Level	@ 1st Difference		
SMEO	-0.356345	-4.467532*	I(1)	Stationary at First Difference
ELEC	-1.466553	-5.634934*	I(1)	Stationary at First Difference
INTR	0.146424	-7.904368*	I(1)	Stationary at First Difference
EXR	4.467453*	-3.241559*	I(0)	Stationary at Level
CRED	0.620874	-3.241559*	I(1)	Stationary at First Difference
CR	4.347643*	-8.378860*	I(0)	Stationary at Level
5% critical value @ Level = -2.97185				
5% critical value @1st diff = -1.95386				

Table 4.1 above shows that SME output (SMEO), electricity consumption (ELEC), interest rate (INTR) and credit to SMEs(CRED) are all stationary at first difference meaning that they are integrated of order one $I(1)$. However, exchange rate (EXR) and crime rate (CR) were both stationary at level which gives an order of integration of $I(0)$. This implies that the variables have mixed order of integration and so necessitates the test for long run relationship using the ARDL Bounds test approach to co-integration (Pesaran, Shin and Smith, 2001).

ARDL Bounds Test for Co-integration

A necessary condition for testing for ARDL bound co-integrating test is that each of the variables is integrated of either order one or zero or both (Pesaran, Shin and Smith, 2001). Since the variables have mixed order of integration, we proceeded to estimate the ARDL bounds test. The null and alternate hypothesis for the bounds test is stated below:

H₀: the variables are not co-integrated (No long run relationship exists)

H₁: the variables are co-integrated (There is long run relationship)

The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis if the F-statistics is greater than the upper bound

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critical values at a chosen level of significance i.e. 5%.

ARDL Bounds Test

Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	4.907649	5

Critical Value Bounds

Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.26	3.35
5%	2.62	3.79
2.5%	2.96	4.18
1%	3.41	4.68

Table 4.3 above shows that the F-statistics value of 4.9076 is greater than the upper I(1) bound of 3.79 at 5% level of significance. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis of no long run relationship exists and conclude that the variables have long run co-integrating relationship. This implies that there is a long run relationship between the selected determinants and SMEs output in Nigeria.

Summary of the short run estimates

Selected Model: ARDL(1, 1, 0, 3, 0, 2)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
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ARDL Short Run Estimates

Since the variables were found to have mixed order of integration and were also co-integrated, it becomes paramount to estimate both the short and long run parameters of the model taking note of the lag length. The short run estimates are summarized below as follows:

Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

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SMEO(-1)	0.789201	0.104599	7.544989	0.0000
ELEC	-3.500623	0.501211	-6.984330	0.0077
ELEC(-1)	0.002248	0.001170	1.920445	0.0754
INTR	0.000295	0.003360	0.087715	0.9313
INTR(-1)	-0.003352	0.003567	-0.939597	0.3634
INTR(-2)	-0.006287	0.003258	-1.929679	0.0742
EXR	0.000275	0.000482	0.570838	0.5772
CRED	-0.000520	0.000232	-2.241441	0.0417
CRED(-1)	0.000756	0.000256	2.956277	0.0104
CRED(-2)	-0.000494	0.000258	-1.918306	0.0757
CRED(-3)	0.000444	0.000230	1.932596	0.0738
CR	-0.218191	0.059293	-3.679878	0.0167
C	1.331722	0.717877	1.855086	0.0848
Coint_Eq(-1)	-0.210799	0.045991	-4.583484	0.0135
R-squared	0.899549	Mean dependent var	8.203166	
Adjusted R-squared	0.829163	S.D. dependent var	0.482647	
F-statistic	25.86195	Akaike info criterion	-5.398081	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000	Durbin-Watson stat	1.936288	

The estimated relationship between the determinants of SMEs performance and SMEs output are explained below:

Electricity Consumption has one lag period. The first lag shows a positive relationship between electricity consumption and output of SMEs in Nigeria. There is a projected increase in SMEs output by 0.0022 units in the previous year as a result of increase in electricity consumption. However, this positive effect is not significant as the *p-value* gave 0.0754 which is above the 0.05

critical value. As electricity consumption tends towards the current year, it exerted negative effect on SMEs output decreasing it significantly by 3.5006 units (*p-value* = 0.0077).

Interest rate in the short run model has two lag periods. Thus, the second and first lag periods showed negative relationships between interest rate and SMEs output decreasing it by 0.0063 and 0.0033 units respectively. In the current year, interest rate increased SMEs output by 0.00029 units. The positive effect of interest rate

Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

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on SMEs output in the current year may be attributed to the increased access of SMEs to credit given the prevailing interest rate and the federal governments drive to make capital available to SMEs through various loan schemes. Exchange rate has no lag period as seen in the model. The current year estimate shows that exchange rate has a positive but insignificant short run relationship with SMEs output increasing it by 0.00027 units. This implies that for every unit increase in exchange rate, SMEs in Nigeria responds with a corresponding increase in their output in the short run period. The long run effect remains to be seen as this will be shown subsequently in this analysis.

Furthermore, credit to SMEs has three lag periods. The third lag shows a positive but insignificant short-run relationship with SMEs output. The second lag period has negative and insignificant relationship with SMEs output. The first lag period has positive and significant relationship while the current year has a significantly negative relationship. This is a very interesting estimate as it shows a fluctuating effect spread over the lag periods. Credit to SMEs decreased SMEs output significantly by 0.0005 units in the current year as against the 0.0007 units increase in the previous year. Thus, the fluctuation witnessed in credit to SMEs in Nigeria has exerted a corresponding fluctuating effect on SMEs which culminated in negative slide in SMEs output in the current year.

The effect of crime rate was estimated at 0.21819 (p -value = 0.0167). There was no lag period effect and this implies that the effect of crime rate on SMEs output is only visible in the current year. The coefficient implies that crime rate decreases SMEs output by 0.2182 units and the decrease was significant given the probability value which is less than 0.05 critical value.

Short run convergence and Intercept: The coefficient of the error correction term in the short run model is represented by the one period lag of the model residual cointEq (-1). This coefficient is positive and significant hence it shows that the model has a short run convergence and hence a long run adjustment mechanism ($\beta = -0.2108$; p -value = 0.0167). The value shows that the short run model corrects its previous period's disequilibrium at a speed of 21.08% annually. The 21.08% represents the speed of adjustment of the model to long run equilibrium.

The intercept of the model is estimated at 1.3317 units. This implies that holding the determinants constant at zero, SMEs output in Nigeria increases by 1.3317 units which can be attributed to the effect of other stochastic variables which enhances SMEs performance or output but are not captured in our model.

Long Run Estimates of the ARDL Model

The long run effect is the appropriate representation of the ARDL model. This is summarized in the table below:

Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

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Summary of the Long Run Estimates

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ELEC	0.010679	0.008064	1.324321	0.2066
INTR	-0.044326	0.017208	-2.575959	0.0220
EXR	0.001305	0.000373	3.498659	0.0216
CRED	0.000882	0.001246	0.707446	0.4909
CR	-3.000644	1.195320	-2.510326	0.0173
C	6.317503	0.633866	9.966628	0.0000

Diagnostic Tests of the ARDL Model

Diagnostic tests	Result	Decision Rule
Adjusted coefficient of determination (R^2)	0.8292 = 82.92%	Very Strong fit
Fishers test (F-stat)	25.862 (p-value = 0.0000)	Overall model is significant i.e. jointly significant
Durbin Watson	1.9363	No autocorrelation
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	F = 0.5439 (p-value = 0.5941)	No Serial correlation

Source: Exacted from Eviews9 Output (See Appendix)

The coefficient of determination from Table 4.6 above shows an adjusted R-squared of 0.8292. This shows that the selected determinants could explain up to 82.92% of the total variations in SMEs output in Nigeria. This shows a good explanatory power of the model. Furthermore, the F-statistic value of 25.86 with probability value of 0.0000 entails that interest rate,

electricity consumption, exchange rate, credit and crime rate have joint significant effect on SMEs output in Nigeria. There is no autocorrelation in the model since the Durbin Watson value of 1.9363 tends towards 2 than to 0 i.e. it is closer to two than to zero based on the rule of thumb. Also, the Breusch Godfrey serial correlation test affirmed that there is no serial correlation of the error terms in the model. Figure 4.7 and 4.8 below show the actual and

Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

fitted residual graph and the cumulative sum test.

Fig. 4.7: Actual and Fitted Regression Line

The figure above shows that there is a close relationship between the actual regression line and the fitted regression line. Since both lines move in close relationship, we can conclude that

the estimated model is close to a-priori expectation hence the model can be used for predictive purposes.

Fig. 4.8: Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) Test

Figure 4.8 above shows that the cumulative sum line is within the upper and lower 5% critical value bounds. This means that the model is stable over the period studied. In other words, the stable effect of the determinants of SMEs output (interest rate, electricity consumption, exchange rate, credit and crime rate) is confirmed

Discussion of Findings

The findings made in this study emanated from the model where SMEs contribution to GDP was used as the dependent variable and interest rate, electricity consumption per capita, exchange rate, access to credit and crime rate were the independent variables. The data were subjected to various econometric tests of unit root, bounds test approach to co-integration and Auto regressive Distributed Lag model estimation.

The adoption of the ARDL model is because the data were integrated of mixed order and were found to be co-integrated. The study proceeded with the short and long run estimates which the ARDL model represents.

The theoretical postulation was subjected to econometric analysis using a modified model with the inclusion of crime rate and electricity consumption as key determinants of SMEs performance in Nigeria. The short run estimates from the Auto regressive distributed lag model were estimated; and the result showed that in the short run, electricity consumption decreased SMEs output significantly in the current year. For the long run estimates, electricity consumption turned positive but insignificant. This implies that electricity consumption by SMEs has improved over the long term and this

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has helped to increase the performance of SMEs. However, the gains from electricity consumption by SMEs have not significantly enhanced their performance. The above finding goes a long way to prove that Nigeria's long run growth in the SME sector is being hampered by electricity consumption. This finding negates that of Nkoro (2019) who found an inverse relationship between SMEs power supply and their performance.

Again, the short run analysis showed that as interest rate increases, SMEs output also increases but not significantly. However, there was inverse effect of interest rate on SMEs output in the long run. The long run negative effect of interest rate agreed with previous finding of Ogundele and Okoya (2020) who studied the effect of macroeconomic instability and SME growth in Nigeria and Orogbo, Onyeizughe and Chukwuma (2017) who using OLS technique investigated the implications of economic environment of SME on economic growth in Nigeria. One very interesting fact about the long run coefficient of interest rate in the model is that it decreased SMEs output significantly. This implies that as interest increases, the SMEs are discouraged from borrowing and this limits their access to capital.

The effects of exchange rate on SMEs output was positive in both short and long run. However, it was only positively significant in the long run. The above finding is in conformity with the result

of (Edoko et al., 2018), who examined the impact of exchange rate on the performance of SMEs by using the Ordinary Least Square technique of analysis. The implication of this is that exchange rate effect on SMEs is very severe and as exchange rate increases, SMEs are affected negatively by way of increased cost of production, and increased cost of acquisition of products for sale. When this happens, there is bound to be decrease in their output since their profitability is tightened. However, SMEs cushion this effect by increasing their prices and trying to break-even in the face of harsh and fluctuating exchange rate. This may lead to increased effect of exchange rate on SMEs output as seen in the short run model estimates and the positive effect is sustained even in the long run because SMEs have found a way of cushioning the effect of increasing exchange rate.

Furthermore, still in the short run, access to credit by SMEs significantly decreases their output. This is because interest rate is high and there is no motivation to borrow. With low access to credit, SMEs output is decreased and this leads to closing down of many SMEs. In the long run, access to credit exerted positive but insignificant effect on SMEs output, This is in variance with study of Oaya and Mambula (2017), who studied the impact of SMEs financing on business growth and found that credit had a significant impact on business growth, which is attributable to the effect of

Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

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increased government intervention on SMEs. Notwithstanding the positive effect of access to credit on SMEs output, there is still insignificant growth in SMEs which calls for more credit injection into SMEs in Nigeria.

Further analysis of the model shows that crime rate exerted a significantly negative effect on SMEs output both in the short run and long run. The reason for this may not be far-fetched. The increasing wave of crime in Nigeria stemming from insecurity has heightened tension amongst SMEs and this may have had inverse effect on SMEs performance. Studies on crime were disaggregated. For instance, Adeleke et al (2020) found a negative correlation between armed robbery and SMEs performance in Lagos State, Nigeria. Asogwa, O., Ibrahim, R., & Oyedepo, J. (2023), established that armed robbery attack led to early business closures in high risk area. Adebayo and Lawal (2022) found that investor confidence declined by 45% in areas prone to kidnapping leading to a reduction in SME investment. These independent studies on different forms of crime corroborates the finding of this study which explicitly proved that crime rate exerts a significant negative effect on the performance of SMEs in Nigeria.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

This study investigated the determinants of performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria between the periods 1986-2024. The study adopted the econometric

procedure in analyzing the data focusing on the Auto regressive distributed lag model technique. After careful analysis of data on electricity consumption, interest rate, exchange rate, access to credit and crime rate, the study concludes that interest rate, exchange rate and crime rate are significant determinants of SMEs performance in the long run while electricity consumption, access to credit and crime rate are the significant determinants of SMEs performance in the short run.

The conclusion emanating from the study implies that what SME need in order to enhance their output in the short term is electricity, access to credit and reduction in crime rate. When the long run is considered, what SMEs require in order to improve their performance is lower interest rate, lower exchange rate and reduced crime rate. Thus, this is a very valid conclusion given the fact that the Nigerian economy is predominantly SMEs-based and so improving on these determinants will ensure long term growth of various SMEs in the country.

On the way forward to enhance electricity consumption, the study recommends that industrial clusters should be set up with exploration of alternative energy sources such as solar, wind etc. To mitigate the effect of high interest rate, the Central Bank of Nigeria must reduce the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) that will prevent commercial banks and other lending institutions from giving out loans at double

Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

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digits. These will make the needed capital to be easily accessible. In navigating the issue of high exchange rate, mass, quality domestic production must be encouraged to the extent

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Ogu Callistus Ike Chigozie, C Mbadugha Onyebuchi, Augustine and Opara Peterdamian

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